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MELT FLOW INVESTIGATION OF BUTADIENE NITRILE RUBBER MODIFIED WITH CHLORINATED POLYISOPRENE

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Abstract

Research has been conducted to study the effect of chlorinated polyisoprene on the rheological properties of butadiene-nitrile rubber under the influence of different temperatures and stresses. The volume consumption of alloys of binary mixtures of butadiene-nitrile rubber chlorinated polyisoprene under the conditions of temperature and stress was studied and the appropriate processing mode was determined. According to the analysis of the obtained results, the rheological properties of alloys of SKN-40/ chlorinated polyisoprene mixtures are expedient to process the amount of chlorinated polyisoprene in this binary mixture by taking 4-5 mass parts and at a temperature of 150°C .

Keyword: Butadiene-nitrile rubber, chlorinated polyisoprene, binary compounds, alloy volume consumption, different temperatures and stresses.

Compositions based on butadiene and acrylic nitrile acid copolymer (Butadiene-nitrile rubber BNR) are used in various sectors of the economy, such as petrochemistry, mechanical engineering, aviation, etc. widely used in industries. In order to improve the structure of butadiene-nitrile rubber and the technical and special properties of the product based on it, it is combined with various structural and natural compounds,

such as fillers, compounds with functional groups - oligomers, monomers, polymers, etc. is added (1). For this purpose, in our research, we obtain double binary mixtures with mechano-chemical modification of butadiene-nitrile rubber (SRN-40) in different proportions with highly dispersed chlorinated polyisoprene (CPI).

Table 1

The composition of the binary mixture SRN-40 /CPI is as follows

N	THE CODE OF THE MIXTURE	1A	2A	3A	4A	5A	6A
	COMPONENTS						
1	SRN-40	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	CPI	-	2	4	6	8	10
	Total	100	100	100	100	100	100

Binary mixtures were prepared on the laboratory apparatus at a temperature of 40 -60⁰ C for 4-6 minutes.

Before obtaining a composite material based on the SRN-40/CPI binary system, we consider it expedient to prepare and study the physical and mechanical properties of the composite materials after studying the rheological properties of the binary system under different temperatures and stresses and determining the optimal ratio and processing process..(3)Rheological properties studied the flow properties of alloys of the binary system SRN-40/CPI at temperatures of 100⁰, 120⁰, 150⁰ and 170⁰ C, under the voltage created by loads of 11.75; 20.85; 26.1 and 32.6 kg.

At low values of stresses on the surface of binary system alloys at temperatures of 100⁰ and 120⁰ C, the nature of the alloy is Newtonian, in other words, it has

a high Newtonian viscosity. As the stress increases, the nature of the alloy changes to a non-Newtonian state. It then has the lowest Newtonian viscosity. As the stress increases, the nature of the alloy changes to a non-Newtonian state. It then has the lowest Newtonian viscosity.

Experimental part

When the (2-6) mass fraction amount of CPI in the SRN-40/CPI mixture, the viscosity of the alloy of the mixture under the influence of all stresses first decreases monotonically (velocity increases) and then increases (when mass the fraction is 2.0). When the amount of CPI in the mixture 6.0 mass fraction , the viscosity of the alloy decreases by two pieces (Figure 1,2). This is due to the fact that CPI has a low molecular weight and acts as a plasticizer when increasing the amount in the mixture. It also interacts with SRN-40

Figure 1. The relation of the flow rate (Q) of the SKN-40 / XPI mixture under the influence of different loads at 100⁰ C with the amount of XPI

Figure 2. The relation of the flow rate (Q) of the SKN-40 / XPI mixture under the influence of different loads at 120⁰ C with the amount of XPI

SRN-40 CPI mixture at a temperature of 150⁰ C and under the influence of the voltage created by the load (11.75;20.85) kg.

When the amount of CPI (2-6) is in parts of the mass, the viscosity of the alloy decreases first compared to SRN-40 (when 2 parts of mass is CPI) and then increases monotonously (volume consumption decreases) (Figure 3). The amount of CPI is the viscosity

of the alloy when the amount of CPI (2-6) in the SRN-40/CPI mixture under the stress created by the load is 32.6 kg. The amount of CPI in the SRN-40 CPI mixture under the voltage created by the load of 32.6 kg. then interacts with SRN-40, where the subsequent increase in CPI (8-10) is partly due to the destruction of SRN-40 rubber and then to the structuring process (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The relation of the flow rate (Q) of the SRN-40 / XPI mixture under the influence of different loads at 155⁰ C with the amount of XPI

At 170⁰ C, when the amount of CPI in the SRN-40/CPI mixture is (2-6) parts of the mass, the viscosity of the system alloy decreases rapidly under a stress of 11.75 kg compared to pure SRN-40 rubber (in the case of a CPI of 2.0 parts of the mass), Under the influence

of (20.85; 26.1;32.6) kg loads, the viscosity of the system decreases sharply. When the amount of CPI in the mixture varies between (2-6) the mass fraction, the viscosity of the mixture increases very rapidly, and the volume consumption decreases (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The relation of the flow rate (Q) of the SRN-40 / XPI mixture under the influence of different loads at 170 °C with the amount of XPI

When the amount of CPI in the SRN-40/CPI mixture is more than 6.0 kg, the alloy does not flow

Figure 4. The relation of the flow rate (Q) of the SRN-40 / XPI mixture under the influence of different loads at 170 °C with the amount of XPI

Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that the composition based on the mixture SRN-40 CPI – 98-94/2-6 can be prepared at a temperature of 50-60°C and processed by vulcanizing at a temperature of 150-155°C to obtain a rubber product with improved properties.

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after a certain period of time (approximately 10 minutes) due to the increase in the viscosity of the system, in other words, the destruction process (Figure 4).

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